

TECHNISCHE
UNIVERSITÄT
WIEN

Data management plan (DMP)

Predictive Modeling of Used Car Prices Based on Market and Technical Attributes

CAR-PRED

Version	Effective date	Description of document/changes
1.0	25/11/2025	First version of the DMP – created for the start of the project

Level of distribution		This DMP is licensed under a Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International License (CC BY 4.0) . DOI: 10.70124/k19vc-wa972
-----------------------	---	---

Project details

Project Coordinator Principal Investigator	Karla Duplic
Contact person (responsible for data management and DMP)	Karla Duplic, e12537798@student.tuwien.ac.at, TU Wien, ROR: ror.org/04d836q62
Contributors	Karla Duplic, e12537798@student.tuwien.ac.at, TU Wien, ROR: ror.org/04d836q62, Researcher
Start date	2025-09-01
End date	2025-11-30
Funder	No external funder; student course project at TU Wien
Funding programme, grant number	No external funder; student course project at TU Wien
Internal project number	Not applicable – student course project, no internal project number assigned

List of acronyms

DMP	Data Management Plan
RDM	Research Data Management
DOI	Digital Object Identifier
CSV	Comma-Separated Values
FAIR	Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, Reusable
PID	Persistent Identifier
ROR	Research Organization Registry
ORCID	Open Researcher and Contributor ID

Content

INTRODUCTION	4
Science Europe practical guide, FAIR data	4
Relevant Policies and Guidelines	4
1. DATA DESCRIPTION	5
1a Lists of datasets that will be reused or produced	5
1b Data generation and reuse	6
2. DOCUMENTATION AND DATA QUALITY	7
2a Data organisation, metadata and documentation	7
2b Data quality control	7
3. STORAGE AND BACKUP DURING RESEARCH PROCESS	7
3a Storage and backup facilities	7
3b Data security and protection of sensitive data	8
4. LEGAL AND ETHICAL REQUIREMENTS	8
4a Personal data	8
4b Intellectual property rights and rights of use	8
4c Ethical issues	9
5. DATA SHARING AND LONG-TERM PRESERVATION	9
5a Data publication and access conditions	9
5b Long-term preservation and deletion of data	10
6. RDM RESPONSIBILITIES AND RESOURCES	10
6a RDM-roles and responsibilities	10
6b Resources	10

Introduction

Science Europe practical guide, FAIR data

A DMP is a structured document that keeps record of what research data is created and what happens to that data during and after a project. It helps with planning the research process and defining responsibilities in a research project involving several researchers or institutions.

For writing this DMP, we followed [the recommendations of Science Europe](#) as they reflect the guidelines agreed upon by the major funders in Europe.

To make our data FAIR, they generally will be treated according to the following criteria:

- We will make our data findable, by uploading it to a data repository that provides a persistent identifier and adding relevant metadata.
- We will make our data accessible by providing open access to data, wherever possible. In cases, where open access is not possible, we will provide meaningful metadata plus contact information for access requests.
- We will make our data interoperable by providing and describing data in a way that is common within our domain by using the same file formats, schemas and vocabularies. We will provide good documentation for all our datasets.
- We will make our data reusable by adding metadata and comprehensive Readme files to all published datasets. The descriptions include details on the methodology used, analytical and procedural information. In case of publication, licenses for code and data will always be assigned and clearly marked.

Relevant Policies and Guidelines

- European Commission's document on Ethics and Data Protection: https://ec.europa.eu/info/funding-tenders/opportunities/docs/2021-2027/horizon/guidance/ethics-and-data-protection_he_en.pdf
- Other (e.g. from a project partner)

1. Data description

1a Lists of datasets that will be reused or produced

Produced datasets

dataset ID	title	type	format	estimated volume	contains sensitive data
P1	Cleaned_Car_Dataset_20251125	Structured text	.csv	< 100 MB	no
P2	Cleaned_YallaMotors_Dataset_20251125	Structured text	.csv	< 100 MB	no
P3	Predictive_Modeling_of_Used_Car_Prices	Source code	.py	< 100 MB	no

Description for "Cleaned Car Dataset":

A cleaned and processed version of the reused dataset, including removal of duplicates, encoding of categorical variables, and selection of relevant features.

Description for "Cleaned YallaMotors Dataset":

A cleaned and processed version of the reused dataset, including removal of duplicates, removal of rows with missing values and removal of whitespace in text values.

Description for "Predictive Modeling of Used Car Prices":

Python code used to preprocess and analyze a reused car price dataset. The script includes several steps essential to the research workflow: - loading an external dataset, - cleaning operations (removal of duplicates), - categorical variable encoding, - saving a cleaned version of the dataset, - feature selection using Recursive Feature Elimination (RFE), - training and evaluating multiple regression models (Linear Regression, Ridge Regression, Random Forest). The code generates a cleaned dataset ("cleaned_car_dataset.csv") which is used in the subsequent modeling steps.

Reused datasets

dataset ID	title	source	rights (e.g. license)	contains sensitive data
R1	Vehicle Dataset	https://www.kaggle.com/datasets/nehalbirla/vehicle-dataset-from-cardekho?select=car+data.csv	CC0-1.0	no

R2	YallaMotors Used Car Sales Data	https://www.opendatabay.com/data/consumer/642f3f41-47ec-4ef9-bf86-063e4f9c0046	DbCL-1.0	no
----	---------------------------------	---	--------------------------	----

The licenses listed for the reused datasets permit their use and redistribution in the context of this project, provided that the original terms are respected.

Description for "Vehicle dataset":

This dataset contains information about used cars. This data can be used for a lot of purposes such as price prediction to exemplify the use of linear regression in Machine Learning.

The columns in the given dataset are as follows: name; year; selling_price; km_driven; fuel; seller_type; transmission; owner.

Description for "YallaMotors Used Car Sales Data":

Used cars listed for sale on the YallaMotors website. It was collected by scraping the site and includes details such as car name, price, engine specifications, brand, and the country of sale. The data is particularly well-suited for exploratory data analysis and developing machine learning models, such as linear regression for price prediction.

Columns:

car name: The full name of the car model.

price: The listed price of the car in the local currency of the country where it is being sold.

engine_capacity: The engine capacity of the vehicle.

cylinder: Information related to the car's engine cylinders.

horse_power: The horsepower of the car's engine.

top_speed: The maximum speed of the car.

seats: The number of seats in the car.

brand: The manufacturer or brand of the car.

country: The country where the car is being sold.

1b Data generation and reuse

Methods and software used for data generation and reuse

Two datasets will be used in the project, both obtained from online repositories, Kaggle (R1) and Opendatabay (R2), in CSV format. The size of both datasets does not exceed 100 MB. The data will be imported, cleaned, and transformed using Python (version 3.12.3) and libraries scikit-learn, NumPy and pandas. Two new, cleaned datasets (P1 and P2) will be created and saved in the CSV format. The Python script (P3) performs data cleaning, categorical encoding, feature selection, and model training. These script is stored under version control in a Git repository on TUGitLab (project 'CAR-PRED'), which records the full change history.

2. Documentation and data quality

2a Data organisation, metadata and documentation

The project files will follow a consistent naming convention: filename_YYYYMMDD.ext, ensuring that different iterations of the datasets can be clearly distinguished over time. Raw data and processed datasets will be stored in separate folders to maintain clarity (/raw, /processed). Version control for the code will be handled using Git and hosted on Github.

For data deposit in the TU Wien Research Data repository, the DataCite Metadata Schema (version 4.4 or the version currently used by the repository) will be applied, as it is the standard supported by TU Wien Research Data. For each dataset the mandatory and recommended fields offered by the repository form will be provided, including title, abstract, creators with affiliation, contact person, license, resource type, and keywords. Keywords will include terms such as 'used cars', 'price prediction', 'machine learning', 'regression', and 'vehicle dataset' to support discovery.

The project source code will be stored in a Git repository on TUgitLab (<https://gitlab.tuwien.ac.at>), which preserves the version history and metadata such as repository name, contributors, and commit log.

Documentation to support validation of the data analysis and to facilitate future reuse will be provided alongside the datasets and code. This will include:

The README for the data. It will contain:

- Project title and short description.
- File list and explanation of each file.
- Description of each variable (name, type, units, allowed values).
- Description of preprocessing and quality checks (e.g., removal of duplicates, handling of missing values, range checks).
- Information on licenses, citation and how to acknowledge the data.
- Information on how this dataset relates to other datasets and to the source code.

The README for the code, with the following information:

- Overview of the purpose of the scripts.
- Software and libraries required (Python version, pandas, NumPy, scikit-learn, etc.).
- Installation and execution instructions, including command examples and parameters.
- Description of input and output files.
- Version information and link to the repository.

2b Data quality control

The following data quality checks will be done: data entry validation, specifically:

- Handling of missing values;
- Detection and removal of duplicates;
- Split into train/test, cross-validation, and performance metrics for models.

3. Storage and backup during research process

3a Storage and backup facilities

For the duration of the project, storage and backup of data will be ensured by Karla Duplic (acting as the person responsible for data management and DMP) in cooperation with the system operator. The data will be stored on the servers of TU Wien.

R1 (Vehicle dataset), R2 (YallaMotors Used Car Sales Data), P1 (Cleaned Car Dataset), P2 (Cleaned YallaMotors Dataset) will be stored on TUcloud: TUcloud is a sync&share service provided by Campus IT for TU Wien members. It runs on Campus IT servers and offers features known from public cloud systems, such as Dropbox, for example, the exchange of data with authorised persons. Deleted files can be recovered within 180 days.

P3 (Predictive Modeling of Used Car Prices) will be stored on TUGitLab: TUGitLab is an application for managing repositories based on Git provided and managed by Campus IT. Our institute’s administrators will manage GitLab groups, assign project permissions, and appoint external project partners as additional GitLab users. This service is highly available and scalable on the Kubernetes platform.

3b Data security and protection of sensitive data

We pay strict attention to compliance with the relevant institutional and national data protection policies listed in the introduction of this document. At this stage, it is not foreseen to process any sensitive data in the project. If this changes, advice will be sought from the data protection specialist at TU Wien, and the DMP will be updated.

Access to data during research:

dataset ID	selected project members	all other project members	the public
P1	writing	reading only	reading only
P2	writing	reading only	reading only
P3	writing	reading only	reading only
R1	writing	reading only	reading only
R2	writing	reading only	reading only

4. Legal and ethical requirements

4a Personal data

At this stage, it is not foreseen to process any personal data in the project. If this changes, advice will be sought from the data protection specialist at TU Wien, and the DMP will be updated.

4b Intellectual property rights and rights of use

The following individual(s) hold rights and control access to the project data:

Reused datasets:

- Kaggle dataset – Access controlled by the original provider (Kaggle). Within the project, access is controlled by the project coordinator (Karla Duplić).

- Yalla Motors dataset – Access controlled by the original provider (Yalla Motors). Within the project, access is controlled by the project coordinator (Karla Duplić).

Access rights for generated datasets:

- Cleaned Kaggle dataset (“cleaned_car_dataset.csv”) – Created during the project. Full access and control rights are held by the project coordinator (Karla Duplić).

- Cleaned Yalla Motors dataset – Created during the project. Full access and control rights are held by the project coordinator (Karla Duplić).

Access rights for associated source code:

- The Python script used for data cleaning and modeling are created by me. Access is controlled by the project coordinator (Karla Duplić).

4c Ethical issues

No particular ethical issue is foreseen with the data to be used or produced by the project. This section will be updated if issues arise.

5. Data sharing and long-term preservation

5a Data publication and access conditions

As far as possible, obtained datasets will be published in repositories. Details on access conditions, reuse licenses, reasons for restrictions, etc. are collected in the table below.

dataset ID	access conditions	estimated publication date	location for publication (repository)	PID	license
P1	Open	2025-11-30	TU Wien Research Data	DOI	CC0-1.0
P2	Open	2025-11-30	TU Wien Research Data	DOI	CC0-1.0
P3	Open	2025-11-30	TU Wien Research Data	DOI	Apache-2.0

Each dataset and the code will receive its own DOI in TU Wien Research Data.

TU Wien Research Data is an institutional repository of TU Wien to enable storing, sharing and publishing of digital objects, in particular research data. It facilitates the funders' requirements for open access to research data and the FAIR principles by making research output findable, accessible, interoperable, and reusable. A DOI is assigned to each dataset published in TU Wien Research Data. This service is developed by the TU Wien Center for Research Data Management and hosted by TU.it. <https://researchdata.tuwien.at/>

Methods or software needed to access and use data: The reused datasets (Kaggle and Yalla Motors) and the cleaned datasets generated during the project are all stored in the standard CSV format. These files can be accessed and reused with any common data analysis or spreadsheet software (e.g., Excel, LibreOffice, Google Sheets) or with programming languages such as Python or R. No proprietary tools are required. The project's source code is provided as plain Python (.py) files. Reuse requires a standard Python environment (e.g., Anaconda, Jupyter Notebook, or any Python 3 installation) and

commonly used open-source libraries such as pandas, NumPy, and scikit-learn. All required packages are freely available. No specialized or commercial software is needed to access or reuse any of the project's data or code.

5b Long-term preservation and deletion of data

dataset ID	location for long-term storage	minimum retention period (≥ 10 years)	foreseeable research uses and/or users
P1	TU Wien Research Data	10 years	<p>Data Scientists: For training and testing regression models and performing EDA.</p> <p>Machine Learning Engineers: To build predictive pricing engines for the automotive sector.</p> <p>Market Analysts: To study pricing trends and brand popularity in the used car market.</p> <p>Students and Researchers: For academic projects related to data analysis and automotive trends.</p>
P2	TU Wien Research Data	10 years	
P3	TU Wien Research Data	10 years	

6. RDM responsibilities and resources

6a RDM-roles and responsibilities

The student researcher (Karla Duplić) is responsible for ensuring metadata production, day-to-day cross-checks and back-up.

6b Resources

There are no costs dedicated to data management and ensuring that data will be FAIR.